

60 Common Aquatic Weed Identification of Bangladesh

Sourav Kanti Bala

Undergraduate student of agriculture
International University Of Business Agriculture & Technology
IUBAT, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Introduction

Aquatic weeds pose a considerable challenge in Bangladesh, affecting the country's extensive water bodies, including rivers, lakes, and wetlands. Species like *Eichhornia crassipes* (water hyacinth), *Pistia stratiotes* (water lettuce), and *Alternanthera philoxeroides* (alligator weed) have become highly invasive, disrupting both aquatic ecosystems and human activities. Water hyacinth is particularly problematic, spreading rapidly and forming dense mats that impede fishing, navigation, and irrigation (Islam et al., 2018). The proliferation of these species is attributed to Bangladesh's tropical climate, nutrient-rich waters, and unregulated disposal of organic waste, which creates ideal conditions for weed growth.

The dense mats formed by these aquatic weeds not only obstruct water flow but also increase the risk of flooding in agricultural fields during the rainy season. This results in prolonged waterlogging, making land unsuitable for farming (Ahmed et al., 2020). Additionally, aquatic weeds compete with cultivated plants for nutrients, further decreasing soil fertility and negatively affecting crop health. Farmers in affected regions often struggle with higher production costs due to the need for additional labor and machinery to clear weeds from irrigation networks.

Efforts to manage aquatic weeds in Bangladesh's agricultural landscape include mechanical removal, chemical treatments, and biological control methods. However, these strategies have been met with varying degrees of success. Chemical control, while effective in the short term, can lead to environmental degradation, affecting water quality and soil health (Rahman, 2021). A more sustainable approach is required, focusing on integrated weed management to protect both agricultural productivity and environmental integrity.

Aqueatic weed Classification

An aquatic weed is a plant that grows partially or completely in water and becomes problematic when it interferes with the use of water bodies for purposes such as irrigation, navigation, recreation, or ecological balance. These plants can proliferate rapidly, outcompeting native species, obstructing waterways, and impacting biodiversity.

Withers, B. (1980). *Weeds in Water*.

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Habitat:

RE- Rooted Emergent; RF- Rooted Floating; FF- Free-Floating; NWE- Near The Water Edge; RS- Rooted Submerged; Rs- Rootless Submerged; WSC-Water Surface Creeper; SF- Submerged And Floating.

Pistia stratiotes L.

Plant Description

Habit : It is a free-floating aquatic plant that forms dense mats on the surface of the water.

Stem : The plant has a very short, spongy stem that remains mostly hidden below the rosette of leaves, with runners or stolons extending to produce new plantlets.

Leaves : The leaves are light green, thick, and velvety, forming a rosette shape. They are obovate or spoon-shaped with wavy margins and measure 2–15 cm long. Fine hairs on the surface make the leaves water-repellent.

Fruit : The fruit is a small, greenish berry that forms underwater. It contains many seeds, which are dispersed by water, though the plant primarily spreads vegetatively through stolons.

Flowers: The flowers are small and inconspicuous, located at the center of the leaf rosette. The plant has unisexual flowers, with both male and female flowers growing on the same plant. They are pale in color and largely hidden beneath the foliage.

Scientific name : *Pistia stratiotes*

Common name : Water lettuce

Local name : Topapana

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Monocots

Order: Alismatales

Family: Araceae

Genus: *Pistia*

Species: *P. stratiotes*

Spirodela polyrrhiza (L.)

Plant Description

Habit : It floats on the surface of still or slow-moving freshwater bodies. It forms dense mats that can cover the water surface.

Stem : The plant has no true stem; instead, it consists of a small, flattened thallus (the plant body) that resembles a small, rounded disc or oval.

Leaves : The thallus acts as both leaf and stem, and it is typically 1-2 mm wide, green, and smooth. It often has a slightly wrinkled appearance and can be slightly lobed at the edges.

Fruit : The fruit is a small, rounded, and usually single-seeded structure that develops from the fertilized flower. It is also not very prominent and is adapted for water dispersal.

Flowers: *Spirodela polyrrhiza* produces tiny, inconspicuous flowers that are often not easily noticeable. The flowers are usually embedded within the plant's thallus.

Scientific name : *Spirodela polyrrhiza*

Common name : Geant duckweed

Local name : Sonapana

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Monocots

Order: Arales

Family: Araceae

Genus: *Spirodela*

Species: *S. polyrrhiza*

Lemna minor L.

Plant Description

Habit : It is a free-floating, tiny aquatic perennial plant, that forms dense colonies and reproduces mainly vegetatively.

Stem : Reduced to a small, almost nonexistent structure. Instead, *Lemna minor* consists mainly of a flattened, leaf-like structure called a frond, which performs photosynthesis.

Fronds : The fronds are small, green, oval, and flat, usually between 1.5 to 4 mm long. Each frond has one to three veins and floats on the water surface. They have air-filled spaces that help them float.

Fruit : The fruit is a tiny, single-seeded structure known as a utricle, although it rarely develops because reproduction is primarily through vegetative propagation.

Flowers: The flowers are extremely small, rarely visible, and inconspicuous. They are produced in a minute pouch at the edge of the frond. *Lemna minor* is mostly asexual, reproducing vegetatively through budding rather than relying on flowering.

Scientific name : *Lemna minor*

Common name : Duckweed

Local name : Khudipana

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Monocots

Order: Alismatales

Family: Araceae

Genus: *Lemna*

Species: *L. minor*

Wolffia arrhiza (L.) Wimm.

Plant Description

Habit : Floating and free-floating; forms small, spherical or oval-shaped colonies on the surface of still or slow-moving water.

Stem : Lacks a true stem; the plant is composed of a single, small, flattened structure.

Leaves: Highly reduced; the plant appears as a tiny, leaf-like structure with no distinct leaves.

Flowers: Very small and often hidden within the plant body; reproductive structures are not easily visible.

Fruits: Tiny and generally inconspicuous; develops within the plant body, containing seeds.

Scientific name : *Wolffia arrhiza*

Common name : Rootless duckweed

Local name : sujipana

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Magnoliopsida

Order: Alismatales

Family: Araceae

Genus: *Wolffia*

Species: *W. arrhiza*

Colocasia esculenta (L.) Schott.

Plant Description

Habit : It is a perennial herb grown for its edible corms and leaves, often found in tropical and subtropical regions.

Stem : The stem is thick, upright, and often covered with a fibrous sheath. It supports the large leaves and can be somewhat fleshy.

Leaves : The leaves are large, heart-shaped, or arrow-shaped, with prominent veins and a glossy surface. They are typically supported on long, stout petioles.

Fruit : The fruit is a small, inconspicuous berry that is not commonly eaten. The plant is primarily cultivated for its corms, which are rich in starch.

Flowers: The flowers are small, usually inconspicuous, and appear in a spadix enclosed by a spathe. The plant's primary value is in its edible parts rather than its flowers.

Scientific name : *Colocasia esculenta*

Common name : Chinese potato

Local name : Pani kochu

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Eudicots

Order: Alismatales

Family: Araceae

Genus: *Colocasia*

Species: *T. esculenta*

Cryptocoryne retrospiralis (Roxb.) Kunth.

Plant Description

Habit : It is a perennial herb with a rhizomatous root system. The plant typically grows submerged in water or in wet soil along riverbanks.

Stem : The stem is short and often not prominent, with the leaves emerging directly from the rhizome.

Leaves : The leaves are linear to lanceolate, with a characteristic spiraling twist. Their surface is often wrinkled, and the color varies from green to reddish-brown, influenced by light and growing conditions.

Fruit : The fruit is a berry-like structure, small and inconspicuous. After flowering, the spathe withers, and the fruit develops beneath the water or soil surface.

Flowers: The flowers are borne on a spadix, surrounded by a narrow, tubular spathe that is greenish or brownish. The spadix contains both male and female flowers, indicating that the plant is monoecious.

Scientific name : *Cryptocoryne retrospiralis*

Common name : Antispiral water trumpet

Local name : Basori

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Monocots

Order: Alismatales

Family: Araceae

Genus: *Cryptocoryne*

Species: *C. retrospiralis*

Sagittaria latifolia Willd.

Plant Description

Habit : It typically grows in shallow water, marshes, and along pond and stream edges. The plant often forms dense stands.

Stem : The stems are usually submerged or floating and can be relatively short, with some species having elongated stems that help support the plant in the water.

Leaves : The leaves are distinctive, with a broad, arrowhead-shaped blade. They are usually green and can range in size from small to large. The leaves are generally arranged in a rosette.

Fruit : The fruit is a small, ovoid to ellipsoid capsule that contains numerous seeds. The capsule is typically about 1 cm long and is released when mature.

Flowers: The flowers are produced on a spike or raceme and are usually white or occasionally pink. Each flower has three petals and three sepals, and they bloom from summer to early fall.

Scientific name : *agittaria latifolia*

Common name : Arrowhead

Local name : Dal kochu

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Monocots

Order: Alismatales

Family: Alismataceae

Genus: *Sagittaria*

Species: *S. latifolia*

Sagittaria latifolia Willd.

Plant Description

Habit : It is a herbaceous, annual or perennial plant, often found in moist, shaded areas such as forests or grasslands.

Stem : The stem is green, slender, and slightly fleshy. It may root at the nodes, enabling the plant to spread. The stem is generally smooth but may have fine hairs.

Leaves : The leaves are alternate, simple, and lance-shaped to ovate. They have smooth edges and are attached to the stem by short petioles. The leaves are generally bright green, with a prominent midrib and a sheath at the base that encloses part of the stem.

Fruit : The fruit is a capsule containing small, irregularly shaped seeds.

Flowers: The flowers are small, with bright blue or violet petals. They grow in clusters and are partially enclosed in a leafy bract (spathe). The flowers are typically composed of two larger petals and one smaller petal, with delicate stamens in the center.

Scientific name : *Commelina appendiculata*

Common name : Asiatic dayflower

Local name : Kanai dogra

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Monocots

Order: Alismatales

Family: Alismataceae

Genus: *Sagittaria*

Species: *S. latifolia*

Limnocharis flava L.

Plant Description

Habit : It is an aquatic or semi-aquatic perennial herb growing up to 1 meter tall. It forms clumps and often grows in clusters in wetlands, shallow waters, and rice fields.

Stem : The stem is erect or decumbent, spongy, and fleshy, sometimes short and submerged, with long petioles supporting the leaves above water.

Leaves : The leaves are broad, ovate, or heart-shaped (cordate) with long, fleshy petioles. They are glossy green, with a wavy margin, and can be up to 15 cm long and 12 cm wide.

Fruit : The fruit is an oblong, dehiscent capsule, about 1 cm long, containing many small, rounded seeds.

Flowers: The flowers are bright yellow, arranged in a loose terminal umbel (a cluster of flowers with stalks of equal length originating from a common point). Each flower has three petals and six stamens, and is about 1.5–2.5 cm in diameter.

Scientific name : *Limnocharis flava*

Common name : Yellow velvetleaf

Local name : Haladepana

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Monocots

Order: Alismatales

Family: Alismataceae

Genus: *Limnocharis*

Species: *L. flava*

Alternanthera philoxeroides (Mart.) Griseb.

Plant Description

Habit : It forms dense mats on the surface of still or slow-moving water bodies, such as ponds, ditches, and rice paddies. It spreads through both vegetative propagation and fragmentation.

Stem : Hollow, creeping or floating, and can extend up to several meters. The stem is slightly woody at the base in mature plants and can root at the nodes.

Leaves : Opposite, simple, lance-shaped (elliptic) leaves, about 2–7 cm long, with smooth edges. The leaves are usually bright green and have a prominent midrib.

Fruit : A small, dry, one-seeded capsule, but seed production is rare in many areas where the plant has been introduced.

Flowers: The flowers are small, white, and grow in dense, round clusters (globular heads) at the end of short stalks. They are mostly axillary (arising from the leaf axils).

Scientific name : *Alternanthera philoxeroides*

Common name : Alligator weed

Local name : Malancha

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Eudicots

Order: Caryophyllales

Family: Amaranthaceae

Genus: *Alternanthera*

Species: *A. philoxeroides*

Cartophyllum demersum (L.) J.R. Fisher.

Plant Description

Habit : It is an aquatic plant typically found submerged in freshwater environments.

Stem : The stems are slender, flexible, and often branched. They can grow to significant lengths, providing a dense underwater habitat.

Leaves : The leaves are finely divided and arranged in whorls along the stem. They are usually green and help in photosynthesis.

Fruit : It does not produce conspicuous fruits as many flowering plants do; reproduction is mainly through vegetative fragmentation.

Flowers: The plant is generally non-flowering in the conventional sense; it primarily reproduces through vegetative means rather than flowers.

Scientific name : *Cartophyllum demersum*

Common name : Coontail

Local name : Kata jhanji

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Eudicots

Order: Lamiales

Family: Acanthaceae

Genus: *Cartophyllum*

Species: *C. demersum*

Hygrophila auriculata (Schumach.) Heine.

Plant Description

Habit : A robust, erect, annual or perennial herb, often found in moist, marshy areas and along riverbanks. It can grow up to 1.5 meters in height.

Stem : The stem is quadrangular, often thick and spongy at the nodes, with a slightly pubescent texture.

Leaves : The leaves are opposite, simple, and lanceolate to ovate in shape. They are 5–15 cm long, with serrated margins and a rough, hairy surface.

Fruit : The fruit is a linear, capsule-like structure containing numerous small, flattened seeds. The capsule bursts open when mature, dispersing the seeds.

Flowers: Flowers are bluish-purple and arranged in axillary or terminal spikes. They are small and tubular, with a bilabiate corolla and prominent bracts.

Scientific name : *Hygrophila auriculata*

Common name : Marsh barbel

Local name : kulekhara

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Eudicots

Order: Lamiales

Family: Acanthaceae

Genus: *Hygrophila*

Species: *H. auriculata*

Aponogeton natans (L.) Engl. & K.Krause

Plant Description

Habit : Aquatic perennial plant found in still or slow-moving freshwater bodies such as ponds, lakes, and marshes.

Stem : The stems are slender, flexible, and submerged, growing from rhizomes anchored in the sediment.

Leaves : The plant has two types of leaves. The submerged leaves are long and ribbon-like, while the floating leaves are oval or oblong with a leathery texture and have long petioles. The floating leaves are usually green with purplish undersides.

Fruit : The fruit is a small, elongated capsule containing seeds, which are dispersed in water.

Flowers: The inflorescence is an emergent spike with small white or yellowish flowers, which bloom above the water surface.

Scientific name : *Aponogeton natans*

Common name : Floating Lace Plant

Local name : Gachu

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Eudicots

Order: Alismatales

Family: Aponogetonaceae

Genus: *Aponogeton*

Species: *A. natans*

Oxystelma esculentum (L. f.) Sm.

Plant Description

Habit : A climbing, perennial vine typically found in marshy areas, along water bodies, and in wetland environments.

Stem : Thin, flexible, and twining, allowing the plant to climb over other vegetation or structures for support.

Leaves : Opposite, linear to lanceolate (sword-shaped), around 4–8 cm long, with an acute apex and entire margins. The leaves have a smooth surface and a prominent midrib.

Fruit : Long, slender, cylindrical follicles that contain numerous seeds. The seeds are equipped with tufts of silky hairs, aiding in wind dispersal.

Flowers: Small, pale pink to white, and star-shaped. The flowers are borne in small clusters or individually, each with five petals. They have a tubular corolla and are mildly fragrant.

Scientific name : *Oxystelma esculentum*

Common name : Rosy milkweed vine

Local name : Dudh lata

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Eudicots

Order: Gentianales

Family: Apocynaceae

Genus: *Oxystelma*

Species: *O. esculentum*

Enhydra fluctuans Lour.

Plant Description

Habit : It is a floating perennial herb that can form dense mats on water surfaces.

Stem : The stems are thin, flexible, and highly branched. They float on water or may be partially submerged.

Leaves : The leaves are simple, ovate to elliptical, and have a smooth margin. They are typically arranged alternately along the stems and can vary in size.

Fruit : The fruit is a small, smooth, and rounded capsule containing several seeds. The seeds are dispersed by water.

Flowers: The flowers are small, usually white or pale yellow, and are borne in clusters. They have a tubular shape with five lobes.

Scientific name : *Enhydra fluctuans*

Common name : Hingcha

Local name : Helencha

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae
Phylum: Angiosperms
Class: Eudicots
Order: Brassicales
Family: Brassicaceae
Genus: *Enhydra*
Species: *E. fluctuans*

Chara globularis Thuillier.

Plant Description

Habit : Aquatic, typically found in freshwater environments like ponds, lakes, and slow-moving streams. It forms dense underwater mats.

Stem : The plant has a branched, filamentous structure that can be up to 30 cm long. The stem is cylindrical and covered with a tough, ridged surface.

Leaves : The "leaves" are actually called phyllodes in charophytes. They are whorled around the stem in groups of 4-12 and have a segmented, thread-like appearance.

Fruit : Reproduces via zygotes, which develop into spores. These spores disperse and germinate to form new plants. It does not produce fruit.

Flowers: It's do not have flowers. Instead, they reproduce via asexual methods (fragmentation and spore production) or through sexual reproduction involving gametes.

Scientific name : *Chara globularis*

Common name : globular stonewort

Local name : Golakar Stonewort

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Charophyta

Class: Charopsida

Order: Charales

Family: Characeae

Genus: Chara

Species: *C. globularis*

Nitella spp.

Plant Description

Habit : Aquatic, typically found in freshwater environments such as ponds and lakes.

Stem : The plant body is composed of long, slender, and flexible filaments or threads.

Leaves : They lack true leaves; instead, they have a whorled arrangement of fine, hair-like structures along the filaments.

Fruit : They do not produce true fruits; reproduction occurs through the formation of zygospores and other reproductive bodies.

Flowers: *Nitella* spp. do not produce flowers; they reproduce via sexual and asexual means using specialized reproductive structures.

Scientific name : *Nitella* spp.

Common name : Nitella algae

Local name : Nitella

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Charophyta

Class: Charophyceae

Order: Charales

Family: Characeae

Genus: *Nitella*

Species: *Nitella* spp.

Ipomoea carnea Jacq.

Plant Description

Habit : A perennial shrub or small tree, reaching up to 2–3 meters in height.

Stem : The stem is woody at the base, becoming herbaceous as it grows. It is often hollow and green or brownish, with branching that helps the plant spread.

Leaves : The leaves are large, simple, and heart-shaped to lanceolate (elongated). They are green, slightly rough to the touch, and grow alternately along the stem. The leaves may have a pointed tip and smooth or slightly wavy edges.

Fruit : The fruit is a capsule that contains several dark brown to black seeds. The seeds are small, hard, and dispersed by wind or water.

Flowers: The flowers are large, trumpet-shaped, and pale pink to light violet in color. They grow in clusters at the ends of branches. Each flower has five fused petals, forming a funnel, and blooms in the morning, fading by afternoon.

Scientific name : *Ipomoea carnea*

Common name : Gloria-d la manana

Local name : Dholkolmi

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Eudicots

Order: Solanales

Family: Convolvulaceae

Genus: *Ipomoea*

Species: *I. carnea*

Ipomoea aquatica Forssk.

Plant Description

Habit : A semi-aquatic, fast-growing herbaceous plant, often sprawling or floating on water. It is usually found in wetland habitats, including ditches, ponds, and along riverbanks.

Stem : Hollow, trailing stems that root at the nodes when in contact with moist soil or water, allowing it to float on water. The stems are smooth and green to purplish in color.

Leaves : The leaves are simple, alternate, and vary in shape, often lanceolate or arrow-shaped. They are bright green and can be smooth or slightly hairy.

Fruit : The fruit is a small capsule that contains several seeds. The capsule splits open when mature to release the seeds.

Flowers: Funnel-shaped and usually white with a purple center. The flowers are similar to morning glories, as they belong to the same genus, *Ipomoea*. They are borne singly or in small clusters at the leaf axils.

Scientific name : *Ipomea aquatic*

Common name : Water spinach

Local name : Kolmi shak

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Eudicots

Order: Solanales

Family: Convolvulaceae

Genus: *Ipomoea*

Species: *I. aquatica*

Commelina benghalensis L.

Plant Description

Habit : A perennial, sometimes annual, creeping or sprawling herb. It often grows in disturbed soils.

Stem : The stem is soft, branched, and may either grow upright or sprawl along the ground. It is green to purple, smooth, and can root at the nodes when it touches the soil.

Leaves : The leaves are alternate, simple, and lance-shaped (elliptic to ovate). They are slightly fleshy and covered with fine hairs, with a prominent midrib and smooth or slightly wavy edges. The leaf base has a sheath that wraps around the stem.

Fruit : The fruit is a capsule that contains several small seeds. The seeds are irregular in shape and are dispersed easily, contributing to the plant's invasive nature.

Flowers: The flowers are small, with bright blue petals (sometimes violet or white). They occur in clusters within a boat-shaped bract, known as a spathe, which partially encloses the flower cluster. The flowers have two prominent larger petals and one smaller petal.

Scientific name : *Commelina benghalensis*

Common name : Dayflower

Local name : Kanai bashi

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Monocots

Order: Commelinales

Family: Commelinaceae

Genus: Commelina

Species: *C. benghalensis*

Scirpus mucronatus L.

Plant Description

Habit : It is a perennial, herbaceous plant that typically grows in wetlands, marshes, or along the edges of water bodies.

Stem : The plant has a triangular, often stiff, and ribbed stem that can grow up to 1 meter (3 feet) in height.

Leaves : The leaves are typically narrow and grass-like, with a basal arrangement. They are usually reduced or absent in the flowering part of the plant.

Fruit : The fruit is a small, achene-like nutlet that contains a single seed. It is usually surrounded by the bracts and scales of the inflorescence.

Flowers: The inflorescence is a dense cluster of small, brownish or greenish flowers. The flowers are typically unisexual and arranged in spikelets.

Scientific name : *Scirpus mucronatus*

Common name : Bog bulrush

Local name : Soktochechra

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Monocots

Order: Poales

Family: Cyperaceae

Genus: *Scirpus*

Species: *S. mucronatus*

***Actinoscirpus grossus* (L.f.) Goetgh. &
D.A.Simpson**

Plant Description

Habit : It is a tall, erect sedge, often found in marshy or wet areas such as swamps, riverbanks, and paddy fields. It can form dense stands.

Stem : The stems are cylindrical, erect, and robust, often reaching heights of 1-2 meters. They are smooth and can be either triangular or round in cross-section.

Leaves : Leaves are long, narrow, and grass-like, arising from the base of the plant. They have a V-shaped cross-section and can be as long as the stems.

Fruit : The fruit is a small, dry achene (nut-like seed) enclosed in a bract, which helps in dispersal.

Flowers: The inflorescence is a cluster of small, brownish to greenish spikelets. The flowers are typically grouped in a branched, open cluster at the top of the stem.

Scientific name : *Actinoscirpus grossus*

Common name : Swamp Rice Grass

Local name : Kasuru

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Monocots

Order: Poales

Family: Cyperaceae

Genus: *Actinoscirpus*

Species: *A. grossus*

Sesbania bispinosa (Jacq.) W.F.Wight.

Plant Description

Habit : It usually grows as a bushy shrub with a spreading habit.

Stem : The stems are often armed with spines or thorns, giving the plant its common name "spiny sesbania."

Leaves : The leaves are pinnate, with small, paired leaflets arranged along a central axis. They are typically green and have a feathery appearance.

Fruit : The fruit is a pod that contains several seeds. It is generally slender, elongated, and can be somewhat flattened.

Flowers: The flowers are typically yellow or orange with a red tinge, arranged in clusters. They are pea-shaped, typical of the legume family.

Scientific name : *Sesbania bispinosa*

Common name : Spiny Sesbania

Local name : Dhincha

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae
Phylum: Angiosperms
Class: Eudicots
Order: Fabales
Family: Fabaceae
Genus: *Sesbania*
Species: *S. bispinosa*

Aeschynomene aspera L.

Plant Description

Habit : It is a low, sprawling or semi-erect plant that can form dense mats. It often grows in wetlands or disturbed areas.

Stem : The stems are slender, branched, and can be either prostrate or slightly erect. They may be hairy or pubescent.

Leaves : The leaves are pinnate with 7-15 pairs of leaflets. The leaflets are small, elliptical, and have a rough texture.

Fruit : The fruit is a flat, dehiscent legume, usually containing 1-2 seeds. It is typically hairy and can be somewhat curved or twisted.

Flowers: The flowers are small, yellow or orange, and form in dense, cylindrical spikes. They are pea-like in structure, typical of the Fabaceae family.

Scientific name : *Aeschynomene aspera*

Common name : Rough Aeschynomene

Local name : Vatshala

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Eudicots

Order: Fabales

Family: Fabaceae

Genus: *Aeschynomene*

Species: *A. aspera*

Ottelia alismoides (L.) Pers.

Plant Description

Habit : An aquatic perennial herb, often found floating on or just below the water's surface in freshwater environments.

Stem : The plant has a rhizome or creeping stem that anchors it in the sediment and extends horizontally.

Leaves : Leaves are broad, ovate to lanceolate, floating, with smooth edges and a waxy texture. They are typically green and can be up to 15 cm long.

Fruit : The fruit is a small, hard, nut-like capsule that contains one or more seeds. The fruit is typically brown and has a rough surface.

Flowers: Flowers are small, white or pale pink, and arranged in axillary spikes. Each flower has three petals and three sepals.

Scientific name : *Ottelia alismoides*

Common name : Alligator weed

Local name : Panikola

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Monocotyledons

Order: Alismatales

Family: Hydrocharitaceae

Genus: *Ottelia*

Species: *O. alismoides*

Vallisneria spiralis L.

Plant Description

Habit : It is a submerged, perennial, aquatic plant commonly found in freshwater bodies like ponds, lakes, and slow-moving rivers. It typically grows in dense, underwater meadows.

Stem : The plant has a rhizomatous growth form. The rhizome is creeping and produces rosettes of leaves. The stem is very short and remains mostly underwater.

Leaves : The leaves are linear, ribbon-like, up to 1 meter long, bright green, flat, with smooth margins and a spiral twist.

Fruit : After pollination, the female flower is drawn underwater and produces a cylindrical fruit with small seeds dispersed into the water.

Flowers: It is dioecious, meaning it has separate male and female plants. Female flowers grow on long, thin stalks that extend to the water surface, where they bloom. Male flowers are smaller, break free from the plant, and float to the surface where pollination occurs.

Scientific name : *Vallisneria spiralis*

Common name : Eel weed

Local name : Pata jhanji

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Monocotyledons

Order: Alismatales

Family: Hydrocharitaceae

Genus: *Vallisneria*

Species: *V. spiralis*

Najas minor All.

Plant Description

Habit : It is a submerged, annual aquatic plant commonly found in still or slow-moving freshwater bodies like ponds, lakes, and canals. It grows fully underwater.

Stem : The stem is slender, branched, and can reach lengths of 20 to 60 cm. It is brittle, often breaking into segments.

Leaves : The leaves are opposite, narrow, and linear, measuring around 1-3 cm in length. They have serrated margins, and the tips can be pointed or blunt. The leaves are usually dark green and flexible.

Fruit : The fruit is a small, one-seeded, ovoid nutlet. It matures underwater and is dispersed by water currents or animals.

Flowers: The flowers are small, inconspicuous, and unisexual. They are borne in the leaf axils, and both male and female flowers are found on the same plant. The flowers lack petals and are wind-pollinated.

Scientific name : *Najas minor*

Common name : Brittle naiad

Local name : Najas

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Magnoliopsida

Order: Alismatales

Family: Hydrocharitaceae

Genus: *Najas*

Species: *N. minor*

Hydrilla verticillata (L.F.) Royle.

Plant Description

Habit : It is an invasive submerged aquatic perennial. It grows in freshwater bodies such as lakes, ponds, and slow-moving rivers.

Stem : The stems are slender, branched, and can grow up to 10 meters long. They are typically covered with small, fine, and often stiff, hair-like structures.

Leaves : The leaves are arranged in whorls of 3 to 8 around the stem. They are narrow, lance-shaped, and typically 1-2 cm long. The margins are often serrated or toothed.

Fruit : The fruit is a small, oval, and green to brownish structure. It is often a seed or a small, floating fruiting body that can help in the dispersal of the plant.

Flowers: The plant produces small, inconspicuous flowers that are usually submerged. They have three white or pale greenish petals and are borne on short spikes that emerge above the water surface.

Scientific name : *Vallisneria spiralis*

Common name : Water thyme

Local name : Hydrilla

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Magnoliopsida

Order: Alismatales

Family: Hydrocharitaceae

Genus: Hydrilla

Species: *H. verticillata*

Hydrolea zeylanica (L.) Vah

Plant Description

Habit : Soft, unarmed, herbaceous perennial, but flowering the first year from seed, therefore seemingly annual, 7-100 cm tall or more, often repent.

Stem : Repeatedly branched, glabrous below the flowering branches

Leaves : Glabrous or very thinly puberulent on the petiole, veiny below, lanceolate to elliptic, 2-12 cm long, 6-12 mm wide, on winged petioles up to 5 mm long.

Fruit : Fruits are capsular type, 4-4.5 mm high, septicidally dehiscent, seated in the persistent calyx. Seeds are numerous, less than 0.5 mm long.

Flowers: Flowers in irregularly bracted racemes or panicles, the inflorescence branches, pedicels, and calyces stipitate glandular; flowers blue.

Scientific name : *Hydrolea zeylanica*

Common name : Ceylon hydrolea

Local name : Hashchara

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Eudicots

Order: Solanales

Family: Hydrophyllaceae

Genus: *Hydrolea*

Species: *H. zeylanica*

Utricularia australis R.Br.

Plant Description

Habit : Aquatic, floating or submerged in shallow water. It forms dense mats on the water surface or along the bottom.

Stem : The plant lacks true stems; instead, it has a series of floating or submerged, branching, filamentous structures.

Leaves : The leaves are highly modified into tiny, bladder-like structures called utricles. These utricles are used for capturing and digesting small prey. The plant also has fine, thread-like leaves that are not as prominent.

Fruit : The fruit is a small, capsule-like structure that contains numerous tiny seeds. The capsule eventually opens to release the seeds into the water.

Flowers: The flowers are small and generally pale yellow, with a lip that is slightly fringed. They are borne on a slender, erect inflorescence that rises above the water surface.

Scientific name : *Utricularia australis*

Common name : Southern Bladderwort

Local name : Jhanjidam

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae
Phylum: Angiosperms
Class: Eudicots
Order: Lamiales
Family: Lentibulariaceae
Genus: *Utricularia*
Species: *U. australis*

Marsilea quadrifolia L.

Plant Description

Habit : A perennial, herbaceous, aquatic fern that grows in shallow water or damp soil. It has a creeping rhizome.

Rhizome: The rhizome is slender, long, and horizontal, growing along the ground or underwater. It anchors the plant while producing roots at nodes and long, thin petioles that bear the leaves.

Leaves : The leaves are compound, each with four leaflets arranged in the shape of a clover, hence the common name "four-leaf clover fern." The leaflets are attached to long, slender petioles that arise from the rhizome. The leaves float or are emergent, depending on water depth.

Fruit : The reproductive structure is a hard, pea-sized sporocarp.

Flowers: It is a fern and does not produce flowers. Like other ferns, it reproduces via spores.

Scientific name : *Marsilea quadrifolia*

Common name : 4 leaved water clover

Local name : Shusnishak

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Tracheophytes

Class: Polypodiopsida (Ferns)

Order: Salviniales

Family: Marsileaceae

Genus: Marsilea

Species: *M. quadrifolia*

Nymphoides aquatica (J.F.Gmel.) Kuntze

Plant Description

Habit : A submerged perennial aquatic plant, primarily found in still or slow-moving freshwater environments such as ponds and lakes. It grows from short rhizomes.

Stem : Short and typically submerged, supporting floating leaves.

Leaves : The leaves are either floating or submerged. Floating leaves are circular or heart-shaped with long petioles, while the submerged ones are often ribbon-like. A distinctive feature is its banana-shaped tubers at the base, which resemble small bananas and help the plant store nutrients.

Fruit : The fruit is a small capsule containing numerous tiny seeds, which are dispersed through water currents.

Flowers: The flowers are white and star-shaped with five petals. They rise slightly above the water on thin stalks, blooming individually or in clusters.

Scientific name : *Colocasia esculenta*

Common name : Banana lily

Local name : Chandramala

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Eudicots

Order: Asterales

Family: Menyanthaceae

Genus: *Nymphoides*

Species: *N. aquatica*

Glinus oppositifolius (L.) Aug.DC.

Plant Description

Habit : It is an annual, prostrate to ascending herb, typically found in open, damp areas such as fields, roadsides, and wastelands.

Stem : The stem is slender, branched, and covered with fine hairs. It is often reddish and grows close to the ground.

Leaves : Opposite or occasionally whorled, oblong to lanceolate in shape, measuring around 1–3 cm long. The leaves are succulent, smooth, and have entire margins.

Fruit : A small, globose capsule that contains numerous tiny seeds. The seeds are released when the capsule matures and splits open.

Flowers: Small, greenish-white to pale yellow, usually occurring in axillary clusters. The flowers are five-petaled, with a subtle appearance, and are bisexual.

Scientific name : *Glinus oppositifolius*

Common name : Slender carpetweed

Local name : Gima-sak

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Eudicots

Order: Caryophyllales

Family: Molluginaceae

Genus: *Glinus*

Species: *G. oppositifolius*

Nymphaea rubra Roxb.

Plant Description

Habit : A perennial aquatic plant that grows in shallow, slow-moving water or ponds. It forms a floating mat of leaves and stems, with a root system anchored in the sediment.

Stem : The stem is thick, fleshy, and rhizomatous, growing horizontally under the water surface. It supports the floating leaves and flowers.

Leaves : The leaves are large, round, and circular with a notch at the base. They float on the water's surface, with a smooth, green surface and red or purple undersides.

Fruit : The fruit is a rounded, greenish-brown to dark brown capsule that develops underwater. It contains numerous seeds.

Flowers: The flowers are large, showy, and typically red to pink. They have numerous petals and are bowl-shaped, emerging above the water on long stalks. The flowers bloom during the day and may last several days.

Scientific name : *Nymphaea rubra*

Common name : Red water lily

Local name : Lal shapla

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Magnoliopsida

Order: Nymphaeales

Family: Nymphaeaceae

Genus: *Nymphaea*

Species: *N. rubra*

Nymphaea nauchali (Burm. f.) Paget ex Roxb.

Plant Description

Habit : It is an aquatic herb that floats on water surfaces, forming rosettes of leaves and flowers.

Stem : The plant has long, slender, submerged stems that anchor it to the sediment at the bottom of water bodies.

Leaves : The leaves are large, circular, and floating, with a smooth or slightly wavy edge. They are typically green and can be up to 30 cm in diameter.

Fruit : The fruit is a small, dry, and dehiscent capsule that releases numerous tiny seeds when mature.

Flowers: The flowers are showy, and white in colour, with multiple petals. They have a star-like appearance and can be up to 20 cm in diameter. The flowers typically bloom in the morning and close by afternoon.

Scientific name : *Nymphaea nauchali*

Common name : Bluish water lily

Local name : Nill shapla

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Magnoliopsida

Order: Nymphaeales

Family: Nymphaeaceae

Genus: *Nymphaea*

Species: *N. nauchali*

Nymphaea alba L.

Plant Description

Habit : An aquatic herb that floats on water surfaces, forming rosettes of leaves and flowers.

Stem : The plant has long, flexible, submerged stems that anchor it to the pond or lake bottom.

Leaves : Large, round, and floating, with a smooth or slightly wavy edge. They are typically green and can reach up to 30 cm in diameter.

Fruit : The fruit is a small, round, and dry capsule that contains numerous tiny seeds, which are dispersed when the fruit splits open.

Flowers: The flowers are usually white, with a pleasant fragrance. They have a cup-shaped structure with numerous petals, and they bloom during the day, typically opening in the morning and closing in the afternoon.

Scientific name : *Nymphaea alba*

Common name : White water lily

Local name : Sada shapla

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Magnoliopsida

Order: Nymphaeales

Family: Nymphaeaceae

Genus: *Nymphaea*

Species: *N. alba*

Nymphaea capensis Thunb.

Plant Description

Habit : Aquatic herb with floating rosettes of leaves and flowers. It is commonly found in ponds and slow-moving water bodies.

Stem : The plant has long, slender, flexible stems that anchor it to the sediment and support floating parts.

Leaves : Large, round, and floating on the water surface. They are typically green with a smooth or slightly wavy margin and can reach up to 30 cm in diameter.

Fruit : The fruit is a small, dry capsule that splits open to release numerous tiny seeds.

Flowers: The flowers are striking, often blue or violet, with a star-like shape. They have numerous petals and are about 15-20 cm in diameter. They generally bloom during the day.

Scientific name : *Nymphaea capensis*

Common name : Cape Blue Waterlily.

Local name : Nill shaluk

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Magnoliopsida

Order: Nymphaeales

Family: Nymphaeaceae

Genus: *Nymphaea*

Species: *N. capensis*

Nymphaea lotus L.

Plant Description

Habit : It is a floating aquatic herb, with large leaves and flowers that float on the surface of the water.

Stem : The stem is rhizomatous (growing horizontally), submerged, and not visible above the water. The rhizome helps to anchor the plant to the substrate while sending up leaves and flowers.

Leaves : The leaves are broad, circular, and floating with a diameter of around 25–40 cm. The leaf margins are slightly undulating or lobed, and the surface may be smooth or slightly hairy. They often have a distinctive split or notch near the stem attachment point.

Fruit : The fruit is a spongy berry, globular in shape, that matures underwater.

Flowers: The flowers are large (10–20 cm in diameter), showy, and usually white with multiple petals. They open at night and close during the day. The fragrance of the flowers is quite distinct. The flowers rise slightly above the water surface.

Scientific name : *Nymphaea lotus*

Common name : Egyptian White Waterlily

Local name : Kumud shaluk

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Magnoliopsida

Order: Nymphaeales

Family: Nymphaeaceae

Genus: *Nymphaea*

Species: *N. lotus*

Euryale ferox Salisb.

Plant Description

Habit : It is a perennial aquatic plant found in shallow freshwater bodies. It floats on the water's surface, featuring large, broad leaves and distinctive flowers.

Stem : The stem is a rhizome that grows horizontally underwater, allowing the plant to anchor itself while producing floating leaves and flowers.

Leaves : The leaves of *Euryale ferox* are large, circular, and float on the water's surface, reaching up to 50 cm in diameter. They have a waxy texture and serrated edges to minimize water loss.

Fruit : The fruit is a spiny, globular capsule that contains several seeds. When mature, the capsule bursts open to release the seeds.

Flowers: The flowers are large and fragrant, typically white or pale purple, with a unique structure. They bloom at night and are pollinated by insects, closing during the day.

Scientific name : *Euryale ferox*

Common name : fox nut,

Local name : makhana

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Eudicots

Order: Nymphaeales

Family: Nymphaeaceae

Genus: *Euryale*

Species: *E. ferox*

Nelumbo nucifera Gaertn.

Plant Description

Habit : Aquatic perennial herb that grows in shallow ponds, lakes, and slow-moving rivers. It can thrive in water depths up to 2.5 meters.

Stem : The plant has long, flexible rhizomes that anchor in the mud, with stout aerial stems (petioles) that rise above the water.

Leaves : The large, circular, peltate (shield-shaped) leaves are bluish-green, with diameters ranging from 30 to 60 cm. The leaves rise above the water surface on long stalks and are water-repellent due to their waxy coating.

Fruit : The fruit is a cone-shaped receptacle containing seeds, called "lotus nuts." As the seeds mature, the receptacle hardens and remains after the petals drop.

Flowers: The flowers are large and showy, ranging from 10 to 25 cm in diameter, typically pink. They are fragrant, with multiple layers of petals, and bloom during the summer. Flowers rise above the water level on separate stems.

Scientific name : *Nelumbo nucifera*

Common name : Pink lotus

Local name : Golapi padmo

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Magnoliopsida

Order: Proteales

Family: Nelumbonaceae

Genus: Nelumbo

Species: *N. nucifera*

Nelumbo nucifera 'Alba Grandiflora' Gaertn.

Plant Description

Habit : Aquatic perennial herb, growing in shallow water.

Stem : Long, flexible rhizomes in the mud, with stout petioles rising above the water.

Leaves: Large, circular, bluish-green, and water-repellent.

Flowers: Large, white, showy, and fragrant blooms.

Fruits: Cone-shaped receptacle with embedded seeds, known as "lotus nuts."

Scientific name : *Nelumbo nucifera* spp

Common name : White lotus

Local name : Shato padmo

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Magnoliopsida

Order: Proteales

Family: Nelumbonaceae

Genus: Nelumbo

Species: *N. nucifera*

Cultivar: 'Alba Grandiflora'

Nelumbo lutea (Willd.) Pers.

Plant Description

Habit : Aquatic perennial herb, growing in shallow ponds and slow-moving waters.

Stem : Long, flexible rhizomes in the mud, with stout petioles that rise above the water surface.

Leaves: Large, round, green, with a waxy coating; often floating on the water.

Flowers: Yellow or creamy white, large, and showy, with a pleasant fragrance.

Fruits: Cone-shaped receptacle with embedded seeds, similar to those of other lotus species.

Scientific name : *Nelumbo lutea*

Common name : American /yellow lotus

Local name : Gomti

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Magnoliopsida

Order: Proteales

Family: Nelumbonaceae

Genus: *Nelumbo*

Species: *N. lutea*

Ludwigia adscendens (L.) H.Hara.

Plant Description

Habit : It is an aquatic or semi-aquatic perennial herb, often forming dense mats in shallow water or muddy soils.

Stem : The stem is typically creeping or prostrate, rooting at the nodes and can be branched.

Leaves : The leaves are alternately arranged, oval to lance-shaped, and have a smooth or slightly serrated margin. They are often succulent and can float on water or be submerged.

Fruit : The fruit is a small, globular capsule that contains several seeds. It dehisces (opens) to release the seeds when mature.

Flowers: The flowers are small, usually yellow, and have four petals. They are often solitary or in small clusters and can be found on short stalks arising from the leaf axils.

Scientific name : *Ludwigia adscendens*

Common name : Water primrose

Local name : Keshordham

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Eudicots

Order: Myrtales

Family: Onagraceae

Genus: Ludwigia

Species: *L. adscendens*

Coix lacryma-jobi L.

Plant Description

Habit : It is an erect, annual herb that typically grows to a height of 0.5 to 2 meters.

Stem : The stem is angular, often winged, and typically green to reddish, with wings that extend downward from the leaf base.

Leaves : The leaves are alternate, lanceolate to linear in shape, and usually measure 5 to 15 cm in length. They have smooth margins and are attached directly to the stem without a petiole.

Fruit : The fruit is a narrow, cylindrical capsule that is about 1.5 to 3 cm long.

Flowers: The flowers are small, with four yellow petals, and are usually found in the leaf axils. Each flower has a tubular base and is about 1 to 1.5 cm across. Blooming typically occurs from summer to early fall.

Scientific name : *Ludwigia decurrens*

Common name : Winged Water Primrose

Local name : Pani Long

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Eudicots

Order: Myrtales

Family: Onagraceae

Genus: *Ludwigia*

Species: *L. decurrens*

Oxalis corniculata L.

Plant Description

Habit : It is a low-growing, spreading herbaceous plant that forms mats or ground cover.

Stem : The stems are weak and often procumbent (spreading along the ground) with a reddish to greenish color.

Leaves : The leaves are trifoliate (three leaflets), with each leaflet being rounded to heart-shaped and often having a slightly toothed margin. They are typically green with a characteristic sour taste.

Fruit : The fruit is a small, rounded capsule that splits open when mature to release the seeds. The capsule is typically smooth and green when young but may turn brown as it dries.

Flowers: The flowers are small, yellow, and have five petals. They are usually found in clusters at the end of the stems.

Scientific name : *Oxalis corniculata*

Common name : Indian sord

Local name : Amrool shak

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Eudicots

Order: Sapindales

Family: Oxalidaceae

Genus: Oxalis

Species: *O. corniculata*

Hygrorayza aristata (L.) J.C. Sm.

Plant Description

Habit : It is a semi-aquatic, perennial herb that typically grows in wetland areas or shallow water.

Stem : The plant has a slender, often creeping or floating stem. It may be partially submerged in water.

Leaves : The leaves are narrow, linear to lance-shaped, and usually arranged alternately. They can be submerged or floating, depending on the water level.

Fruit : The fruit is a small, dry capsule that contains numerous tiny seeds. The capsule is usually dehiscent, splitting open to release the seeds.

Flowers: The flowers are small, tubular, and arranged in dense clusters or spikes. They are usually white or pale pink and may appear above the water surface.

Scientific name : *Colocasia esculenta*

Common name : Asian waterweed

Local name : Jungly dhan

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Magnoliopsida

Order: Lamiales

Family: Orobanchaceae

Genus: *Hygrorayza*

Species: *H. aristata*

Monochoria vaginalis (Burm f.) Kunth.

Plant Description

Habit : A fleshy, tufted, annual or perennial aquatic herb with a glabrous, shiny appearance; 10-50 cm tall.

Stem : A short rhizome.

Leaves : Size and shape is highly variable. In young plants without lamina, the leaves are 2-12.5 cm long and 0.5-10 cm wide. In somewhat older plants, the leaves are floating, linear or lanceolate and in still older plants, are ovate-oblong to broadly ovate, sharply acuminate with a heart-shaped or rounded base, shiny, deep-green, and with longitudinal veins. The petioles are soft and hollow.

Fruit : Capsule, 1 cm in size, splits between the partitions into three valves. Seeds are longitudinally ribbed.

Flowers: The flowers are large and showy, ranging from 10 to 25 cm in diameter, typically pink. They are fragrant, with multiple layers of petals, and bloom during the summer. Flowers rise above the water level on separate stems.

Scientific name : *Monochoria vaginalis*

Common name : heartleaf false pickerelweed

Local name : Chotonakha

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Monocots

Order: Commelinales

Family: Pontederiaceae

Genus: *Monochoria*

Species: *M. vaginalis*

Monochoria hastata (L.) Solms.

Plant Description

Habit : It is a perennial herb, growing in clumps, and can reach heights of around 30–80 cm. It thrives in shallow water or muddy areas.

Stem : The stems are erect, often spongy and hollow, enabling the plant to float in water or remain stable in muddy environments.

Leaves : The leaves are hastate (arrow-shaped), with long petioles that emerge from the base of the plant. The leaf blades are broad with pointed lobes at the base, typically around 5–15 cm in length, green and somewhat waxy in texture.

Fruit : The fruit is a capsule containing numerous small seeds. The seeds are dispersed through water, allowing the plant to colonize new areas.

Flowers: The flowers are borne on erect, spike-like inflorescences, violet to blue in color, and zygomorphic (bilaterally symmetrical). Each flower has six petals, with one often larger and differently colored. They bloom above the water, making them prominent.

Scientific name : *Monochoria hastata*

Common name : arrowleaf false pickerelweed

Local name : Boronakha

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Monocots

Order: Commelinales

Family: Pontederiaceae

Genus: *Monochoria*

Species: *M. hastata*

Eichhornia crassipes (Mart.) Solms.

Plant Description

Habit : It is a perennial aquatic herb, forming dense mats on the surface of freshwater bodies such as ponds, lakes, and rivers.

Stem : The plant has a spongy, erect, and swollen stem called a petiole, which helps it float on water. The petioles are inflated and filled with air cavities.

Leaves : The leaves are thick, glossy, and broad, forming a rosette. They are round to ovate, with a prominent midrib and smooth margins. The leaves are typically around 10-20 cm wide.

Fruit : The fruit is a capsule that contains several seeds, which are dispersed in water. The seeds can remain viable in water for many years.

Flowers: It produces attractive, showy flowers that are purple to lavender with a yellow spot in the center of the upper petal. The flowers grow on a spike and are arranged in clusters, emerging above the foliage.

Scientific name : *Eichhornia crassipes*

Common name : Water hyacinth

Local name : Kochuripana

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Monocots

Order: Alismatales

Family: Pontederiaceae

Genus: *Eichhornia*

Species: *E. crassipes*

Polygonum glabrum Willd.

Plant Description

Habit : It is a semi-aquatic, erect herb or subshrub, growing 1 to 3 meters tall.

Stem : The stem is cylindrical, smooth, hollow, and swollen at the nodes, with reddish or greenish coloration.

Leaves : The leaves are alternate, simple, lanceolate, or elliptic with smooth edges, typically around 10-15 cm long. They have a prominent midrib and tapering tips, and the leaf base is rounded or slightly cordate.

Fruit : The fruit is a small, shiny, three-angled achene (dry, indehiscent) that is dark brown to black when mature.

Flowers: Small, greenish-white or pinkish flowers are arranged in dense terminal or axillary spike-like clusters. They are bisexual, with five tepals, and bloom throughout the year in favorable conditions.

Scientific name : *Polygonum glabrum*

Common name : Polygonum

Local name : Bishkatali

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Eudicots

Order: Caryophyllales

Family: Polygonaceae

Genus: Polygonum

Species: *P. glabrum*

Persicaria orientalis (L.) G. Don.

Plant Description

Habit : It is an annual herb that typically grows upright, reaching heights of 60 to 150 cm. It often forms dense clumps in wet or moist areas.

Stem : The stems are erect, slender, and may be slightly branched. They are typically green to reddish in color and have a smooth or slightly hairy texture.

Leaves : Alternate, simple, ovate to lanceolate, 5 to 15 cm long, with a pointed tip, smooth margin, and a reddish or purplish spot at the base.

Fruit : The fruit is a small, shiny achene, less than 1 cm long, dark brown to black, and dispersed by water or animals.

Flowers: The flowers are small and clustered in dense, spike-like racemes that can be found at the tips of the stems. They are usually pink to reddish and bloom from summer to fall. Each flower has five petals and is surrounded by bracts.

Scientific name : *Persicaria orientalis*

Common name : Prince's Feather

Local name : Bara Panimorich

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Eudicots

Order: Caryophyllales

Family: Polygonaceae

Genus: *Persicaria*

Species: *P. orientalis*

Leersia hexandra Sw.

Plant Description

Habit : It is a perennial, aquatic grass that typically grows in shallow water or wetlands, forming dense clumps.

Stem : The stems are slender, erect, and can grow up to 1-2 meters tall. They are usually smooth and slightly ribbed.

Leaves : The leaves are narrow, linear, and can be up to 30 cm long. They are usually green and have a rough texture along the edges.

Fruit : The fruit is a small, dry, and indehiscent seed, which is often enclosed in a husk or lemma.

Flowers: The flowers are small and arranged in loose, branched clusters called panicles. They are typically inconspicuous and may be greenish or pale.

Scientific name : *Leersia hexandra*

Common name : Southern cut grass

Local name : Arail

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Liliopsida

Order: Poales

Family: Poaceae

Genus: *Leersia*

Species: *L. hexandra*

Limnophila sessiliflora (Vahl) Blume.

Plant Description

Habit : This plant exhibits a sprawling habit, often extending up to 1 meter in length. It commonly found in tropical and subtropical regions. It typically grows in shallow waters, forming dense mats.

Stem : The stems are slender and flexible, with a branching structure that allows for a wide spread in aquatic environments.

Leaves : Leaves are arranged oppositely or in whorls, shaped lanceolate to ovate with finely serrated edges, and are bright green in color.

Fruit : The fruit is a capsule that is elongated and contains multiple seeds, which are dispersed by water movement.

Flowers: Flowers are small and can appear solitary or in clusters, typically pale purple to white, with five lobes, and bloom mainly in the summer.

Scientific name : *Limnophila sessiliflora*

Common name : Ambuliad

Local name : Bamon kasuri

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Eudicots

Order: Lamiales

Family: Plantaginaceae

Genus: *Limnophila*

Species: *L. sessiliflora*

Azolla pinnata R. Br.

Plant Description

Habit : It forms dense mats on the surface of still or slow-moving water bodies, such as ponds, ditches, and rice paddies.

Stem : The plant has slender, branched stems that are horizontal and float on the water's surface. They bear small leaves and roots that hang down into the water.

Leaves : The leaves are tiny and scale-like, arranged in two rows along the stem. They are bilobed, with one lobe floating on the water's surface and the other submerged. The upper lobe is typically green (or reddish-brown in strong sunlight), while the lower lobe is more translucent.

Fruit : as a fern, does not produce fruits but reproduces through spores, housed in specialized structures called sporocarps.

Flowers: It does not produce flowers as it is a fern. It reproduces asexually via fragmentation or sexually through spores.

Scientific name : *Azolla pinnata*

Common name : Mosquito fern

Local name : Kutipana

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Polypodiophyta

Class: Polypodiopsida

Order: Salviniales

Family: Salviniaceae

Genus: *Azolla*

Species: *A. pinnata*

Salvinia natans (L.) All.

Plant Description

Habit : It is a small, free-floating aquatic fern that forms dense mats on the surface of calm, freshwater bodies like ponds, lakes, and slow-moving rivers.

Stem : The stem is short, horizontal, and floats just below the water's surface. It produces roots that do not anchor to the soil but float freely in the water.

Leaves : has two types of leaves: oval, leathery floating leaves that help it float, and finely divided submerged leaves that aid in nutrient absorption.

Fruit : Being a fern, it does not produce fruits or seeds. The plant forms reproductive spores in sporangia, though spore production is rare. Instead, it primarily spreads through vegetative fragmentation.

Flowers: It is a fern, so it does not produce flowers. Instead, it reproduces asexually through fragmentation or spores.

Scientific name : *Salvinia natans*

Common name : Water Fern

Local name : Tilokpana

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Polypodiophyta (Ferns)

Class: Polypodiopsida

Order: Salviniiales

Family: Salviniaceae

Genus: *Salvinia*

Species: *S. natans*

Cryptocoryne retrospiralis (Roxb.) Kunth.

Plant Description

Habit : It is a free-floating aquatic fern that forms dense mats in shallow, slow-moving waters like ponds, lakes, and marshes.

Stem : The stem is typically short and modified into a rhizome, with horizontal growth. It is not usually visible above water, as the plant floats on the surface.

Leaves : The leaves include small, velvety floating leaves with green upper surfaces and purplish undersides, and elongated, feathery submerged leaves that anchor the plant in the water.

Fruit : The plant does not produce typical fruits, as it reproduces primarily through spores. The sporocarps contain the spores, which can disperse in water.

Flowers: It does not produce true flowers. Instead, it reproduces vegetatively through fragmentation and has a sporocarps (spore-bearing structures) for reproduction.

Scientific name : *Salvinia cucullata*

Common name : Asian watermoss

Local name : Indurkani

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Pteridophyta

Class: Polypodiopsida

Order: Salviniiales

Family: Salviniaceae

Genus: *Salvinia*

Species: *S. cucullata*

Sphenoclea zeylanica Gaertn.

Plant Description

Habit : is an erect, annual herb growing 30-100 cm tall, commonly found in wetlands, rice fields, and marshes in tropical and subtropical regions.

Stem : Cylindrical, smooth, and typically unbranched, with a fleshy texture.

Leaves : Simple, alternate, and lanceolate to oblong in shape. The leaves are 5-15 cm long, with a smooth margin, tapering at both ends, and without petioles (sessile).

Fruit : The fruit is a small, capsule-like structure, releasing numerous tiny seeds when mature.

Flowers: Small, white or greenish-white flowers arranged densely in cylindrical spikes (inflorescences) at the ends of the stems. The flowers are inconspicuous but numerous, giving the spike a dense appearance.

Scientific name : *Sphenoclea zeylanica*

Common name : Gooseweed

Local name : Zheel morich

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Eudicots

Order: Solanales

Family: Sphenocleaceae

Genus: *Sphenoclea*

Species: *S. zeylanica*

Trapa natans L.

Plant Description

Habit : It is a floating annual herb that forms dense mats on the water surface.

Stem : The plant has long, flexible stems that float and are anchored to the sediment by roots.

Leaves : It's leaves are deeply lobed and are typically triangular or ovate with serrated edges. They are arranged in a rosette at the surface of the water.

Fruit : The fruit is a hard, spiny nut with a shell that is often used in cooking. It has a distinctive, horn-like structure with spikes that protect the seed inside.

Flowers: The flowers are small, white or pale pink, and usually emerge above the water surface. They are borne in clusters and have four petals.

Scientific name : *Trapa natans*

Common name : Water caltrop

Local name : Paniphal

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Eudicots

Order: Trapales

Family: Trapaceae

Genus: *Trapa*

Species: *T. natans*

Typha latifolia L.

Plant Description

Habit : It is a tall, grass-like plant that can grow up to 2.5 meters in height. It forms dense, clonal stands through rhizome systems.

Stem : The stem is simple, unbranched, and erect, rising directly from the rhizome. It is slender and cylindrical, and typically green in color.

Leaves : The leaves are long, linear, and strap-like, reaching up to 2 cm wide and 1–2 meters in length. They are typically a bright green and are arranged alternately, sheathing the stem at the base.

Fruit : The fruit is small, wind-dispersed, and forms a fluffy, cotton-like mass when mature, aiding in seed distribution.

Flowers: The flowers are produced on a characteristic brown, cylindrical spike. The inflorescence consists of two parts: the upper part, bearing male flowers, and the lower, thicker part, which contains the densely packed female flowers.

Scientific name : *Typha latifolia*

Common name : Common cattail

Local name : Hugla

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Angiosperms

Class: Eudicots

Order: Poales

Family: Typhaceae

Genus: Typha

Species: *T. latifolia*

Spirogyra spp.

Plant Description

Habit : is a filamentous green algae found in freshwater environments, forming green, slimy mats or strands that float or attach to surfaces.

Stem : The plant is composed of long, unbranched filaments, each consisting of a single row of cells. These filaments can vary in length but are generally thread-like.

Leaves : Spirogyra doesn't have traditional leaves. Instead, the cells in the filament contain chloroplasts arranged in a spiral pattern, which is how the algae gets its name.

Fruit : It does not produce fruit. Instead, it forms zygospores during sexual reproduction, which are thick-walled and can survive unfavorable conditions.

Flowers: Spirogyra does not produce flowers. It reproduces asexually through fragmentation and sexually through conjugation.

Scientific name : *Spirogyra* spp.

Common name : Filamentous Algae

Local name : Kambol agacha

Scientific Classification

Kingdom: Plantae

Phylum: Chlorophyta

Class: Zygnematophyceae

Order: Zygnematales

Family: Zygnemataceae

Genus: Spirogyra

Species: *Spirogyra* spp.

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Significance of aquatic weeds

Aquatic weeds play a significant ecological role by providing habitat and food for various aquatic organisms. They support biodiversity in water bodies and contribute to nutrient cycling and oxygenation, which are essential for maintaining healthy ecosystems (Madsen, 2000). Their roots stabilize sediments, preventing erosion and maintaining water clarity, which benefits fish and other aquatic species.

However, excessive growth of aquatic weeds can have negative impacts. Invasive species like water hyacinth (*Eichhornia crassipes*) can disrupt water flow, reduce biodiversity, and hinder human activities such as fishing and navigation (Gopal & Sharma, 1981). This can lead to substantial economic costs for weed management and control. Additionally, dense growth can create anoxic conditions, negatively affecting water quality and aquatic life.

Despite these challenges, some aquatic weeds have practical uses. They can be harvested for biomass, used in biofuel production, or employed in phytoremediation to remove pollutants from water (Denny, 1987). Understanding the dual role of aquatic weeds is essential for effective management and utilization, ensuring they contribute positively to ecosystems and human welfare without causing harm.

• References

1. Islam, M. D., Rahmatullah, S. M., Ahmed, M., Asif, A.-A., Satter, A., Sarker, B., Hossain, A., & Mojumder, S. (2017). Aquatic weeds diversity of Bangladesh Agricultural University Campus, Mymensingh, Bangladesh. *Asian-Australasian Journal of Bioscience and Biotechnology*, 2(2), 181-192.
2. Adhikary, R. K., Alam, M. S., & Asif, A.-A. (2018). Aquatic weeds diversity of Fatki River in Magura district, Bangladesh. *Asian-Australasian Journal of Bioscience and Biotechnology*, 3(3), 201-207.
3. Ashrafuzzaman, M., Jone, M. J. H., & Ashraf, S. B. (2023). Aquatic plants of Bangladesh Agricultural University Botanical Garden: Species diversity and potential uses. *Indian Journal of Ecology*, 50(3), 555-565. <https://doi.org/10.55362/IJE/2023/3935>
4. Hossain, M. A., & Khatun, M. A. (2003). Identification and management of aquatic weeds in freshwater ecosystems of Bangladesh. Bangladesh Agricultural Research Council.
5. Khatun, N., Rahman, M. A., & Rahman, M. O. (2013). Aquatic weeds of southwestern Bangladesh: Diversity and utilization. *Journal of Biodiversity and Environmental Sciences*, 3(2), 90-99. This study explores the diversity, distribution, and potential uses of aquatic weeds in the southwestern region of Bangladesh.
6. Ahmed, Z. U., & Hassan, M. A. (1997). *A Field Guide to Aquatic Weeds of Bangladesh*. Asiatic Society of Bangladesh, Dhaka.